

Strengthening the Life Skills of Home Economics Students: Chronicles of Teachers in the Post-Pandemic Class

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences of home economics teachers in strengthening the life skills of the learners, specifically in Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City. There were eight (8) home economics teachers who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas of the parent participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the group of HE elementary schools in the same division. The virtual in-depth-interview was employed to gather some information as regards to their respective experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as pertains to the experiences and views of the participants: Practicing good communication, strengthening food preparation techniques and guided and appropriate decision making. The coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the students were: building students' capacity, opening to feedback and focusing on basic life skills for the 21st century. The insights drawn from the participants were: understanding the millennial characteristics and enhance practical life skills. The teachers may be more sensitive to the needs of the learners and be watchful on the skills of the learners. These teachers may consider the personal characteristics of the learners. The home economics learners may be guided properly to enrich their knowledge in home economics and improve their skills in cooking but being more knowledgeable on how to live and be healthy.

KEY WORDS

1. Strengthening life skills
2. home economics learners
3. post -pandemic class

1. Introduction

Establishing an excellent life skill at a younger age brings a brighter future in this very uncertain community where we live. There were several demands in keeping a good life in this very complex society. This is true after the onset of the pandemic. So much were changed then, from the sources of food supplies to the ways in making the regular routines in the homes and mingling with others. Looking back in the past activities and routines of people, it has been observed that so much were changed, thus, the need to realign the specific home management skills. The United States competitiveness in the global economy depends on a workforce that has acquired both the technical knowledge needed for specific occupations and the “employability skills” required for all jobs. According to a 2012 survey of 704 employers conducted by The Chronicle of Higher Education and American Public Media’s Marketplace, half of those surveyed said they had trouble finding recent graduates to fill vacancies in their compa-

nies; even though applicants had the technical prowess, they lacked the communication, adaptability, decision-making, and problem-solving skills needed to do the job (Fischer, K. (2013). Heckman, J. J. (2012) claimed that there is a growing divide between the skills employers are seeking and applicants' abilities. As Nobel Prize-winning economist James Heckman notes, this divide should lead to a recognition that U.S. economic success and productivity depend on employees with both cognitive and social and emotional skills, which he calls "character skills." In order for students to achieve success in school, career, and life, they must be taught social and emotional skills—just as they learn reading, math, and science—through instruction and practice. School-based social and emotional learning (SEL) curricula provide a key to workforce development by explicitly teaching the social and emotional skills employers are seeking and the U.S. economy needs. Research shows SEL works to improve behavioral, academic, and career success. In an article written by Lasco (2022) he emphasized that one of the life skills needed by every Filipino citizen was on wellness and nutrition. Health has long been a grade school subject, but much more can be done in equipping young people with the practical health skills to identify nutritious food and actually prepare it as well as to make their bodies fit without resorting to potentially dangerous products and practices from the use of anabolic steroids to resorting to unproven cosmetic procedures. Pacpaco (2023) cited that Isabela 6th

District Representative Faustino "Inno" Dy V is pushing for the approval of his House Bill (HB) Nos. 3607 or the National Research Council of the Philippines Act and 1208 or the inclusion of a Life Skill Course in the curriculum of both in the public and private schools. Dy said that under HB No. 1208, the topics included in the "Course on Life Schools" are the following; Drivers and Pedestrian Education, Education Overview of Taxation, Government 101, Basic Personal Finance, Social Media Literacy and Data Privacy Rights, Career 101 or the production of resumes and the proper answers on interviews. Dy added the bill also seeks to widen the knowledge and ability of the youth so they can be active members in their respective communities and be ready for challenges in life. In the local scenario, particularly in Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City, it has been clearly noticed that the students in the secondary level, specifically in Grade 7, were unworried about their life skills. Despite the fact that this area is quite distant from the urban city, they were simply observed to be very comfortable with what they have as of the moment. They were dependent upon precooked food being sold in the streets. This means that they were all becoming dependent on meals prepared by others. Having this scenario, there are apprehensions that these secondary learners may not be able to hone their life skills, which is a demand in other places such as residing in big cities or urban places in the future.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the ways to strengthen the life skills of secondary learners. This study also scrutinized the coping mechanisms of Home Economics (HE) teachers in strengthening the life skills of their learners. This study also explored the insights of the HE as they viewed the life skills of their students at the secondary level.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aims to specifically answer the following questions:

- (1) What are experiences of HE teachers in strengthening the life skills of the students in the post pandemic class?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the students?

(3) What insights can be drawn to educate the HE learners from the chronicles of the teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Life Skills. Life skills are defined as “a group of psychosocial competencies and interpersonal skills that help people make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathize with others, and cope with and manage their lives in a healthy and productive manner. Life skills may be directed toward personal actions or actions toward others, as well as toward actions to change the surrounding environment to make it conducive to health.” according to World Health Organization (WHO). Bearing the

WHO definition in mind, the Basic Life Skills curriculum offers youth the emotional, social and intellectual tools needed to achieve success in life – on a personal level, an interpersonal level, and within their community and work places (UNICEF, Downloaded March 8, 2023). In this study, this term refers to the students skills and their ability to deal with common life circumstances. Home Economics Students. This term refers to the students in secondary school who are currently enrolled in home economics class of cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao city. Post-Pandemic Class. This term refers to the classes being conducted after almost three years of off-classroom classes. These classes are currently on the face-to-face mode.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies are the beneficiaries. Department of Education Personnel. The DepEd, particularly the ‘officials of Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City to constantly monitor the implementation of home economics curriculum in the area, this ensures that the students and teachers are fully participating in the skills development of all the involved persons in the campus. The home economics teachers. For the home economics teachers to be more diligent in maintaining the expected life

skills of the students that need to be learned as they journey towards improving their lives through the completion of HE competencies. The learners. This study is beneficial to the HE students as this would provide a great information about their current life skills status. This study also provides an idea for the teachers to further explore how the current students are adopting the trends in home economics. The future researchers. This study shall encourage the future researchers to give more attention to life skills of the millennials ad their ways of keeping their values and insights in home economics as a course in the secondary level.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the Theory of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) which is the process of developing the self-awareness, self-control, and interpersonal skills that are vital for school, work, and life success. The concept was initially developed in 1987 when Timothy Shriver and Dr. Roger P. Weissberg. People with strong

social-emotional skills are better able to cope with everyday challenges and benefit academically, professionally, and socially. From effective problem-solving to self-discipline, from impulse control to emotion management and more, SEL provides a foundation for positive, long-term effects on kids, adults, and communities. Children thrive. Schools win. Workplaces benefit. Society strengthens. All due to social-

emotional learning. It is a theory of learning that focuses on helping children develop the capacity to recognize and manage their own emotions, set and achieve goals, understand and empathize with the emotions and experiences of others, build positive relationships, and make responsible and healthy decisions. SEL emphasizes the importance of developing a range of social and emotional skills that are essential for success in both personal and professional settings. By teaching children these skills, we can help them become more well-rounded, empathetic, and resilient individuals. Another theory that supports this study was drawn from the The Five Social Emotional Learning Competencies. According to the Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL), an organization devoted to students and educators to help achieve positive outcomes for PreK-12 students, SEL involves five core competencies that can be applied in both the classroom, at home, and in students' communities. These five core competencies are: Self-awareness. To recognize your emotions and how they impact your behavior; acknowledging your strengths and weaknesses to better gain confidence in your abilities. Self-management. To take control and ownership of your thoughts, emotions, and actions in various situations, as well as setting and working toward goals. Social awareness. The ability to put yourself in the shoes of another person who may be from a different background or culture from the one you grew up with. To act with empathy and in an ethical manner within your home, school, and community. Relationship skills. The ability to build and maintain healthy relationships with people

from a diverse range of backgrounds. This competency focuses on listening to and being able to communicate with others, peacefully resolving conflict, and knowing when to ask for or offer help. The American Association of School Administrators (2023) posited that being life ready means students leave high school with the grit and perseverance to tackle and achieve their goals by demonstrating personal actualization skills of self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness, responsible decision-making, and relationship skills. Students who are life ready possess the growth mindset that empowers them to approach their future with confidence, to dream big and to achieve big. Honing in on 21st century skills is essential to ensuring that students are prepared for college, career, and civic life. This study was further based on the Framework for 21st Century Learning made popular by the Partnership for 21st Century Skills (Mountains, 2017). Describing the skills, knowledge, and expertise students must master to succeed in work and life, the framework combines content knowledge, specific skills, expertise, and literacies. P21 believes that the "base" of 21st century learning is the acquisition of key academic subject knowledge, and that schools must build on that base with additional skills including Learning Skills, Life Skills, and Literacy Skills. Learning Skills: Also known as the "four Cs" of 21st century learning, these include critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity. Life Skills: Flexibility, initiative, social skills, productivity, leadership Literacy Skills: Information literacy, media literacy, technology literacy.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher introduces the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research procedures, participants, data collection, and analysis. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background for the conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research involves selecting the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, for example, among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of home economics

teachers were drawn to elucidate their personal knowledge in strengthening the life skills of their students in the present time.

In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The purpose of this research was to gather important details on the ways by which

the home economics teachers strengthened the life skill of their students in the post-pandemic classes specifically in Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the experiences of home economics teachers in Paquibato District, Davao City. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant's personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a lit-

erary, informal style using the personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to explain the experiences of home economics teachers as they dreamed of strengthening the life skills of their students. As a researcher, I agree with the post-modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, and self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss different subjects and creative ways. In this situation, students learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others' criticism and try to think in a critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also, they emphasize cooperative learning, independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It is deducted that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—This study unleashed the experiences of HE teachers based on their personal sharing of thoughts pertaining to the student's life skills. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of home economics teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a

valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher anticipated that the personal involvements and challenges of the home economics teachers would be ex-

plored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read, reread, and culled for like phrases and themes that were then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. This study's phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

2.4. Research Participants—The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the home economics teachers coming from Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City. All the participants were HE teachers from various nearby schools. They must have been teaching home economics for at least one to three years (1-3). All the participants were coming from the secondary level, regardless of their age, sex and marital status. Further, the informants of this study must have experienced teaching HE during the pandemic, such experience would be able to make them compare the life skills of their students during the pre and post pandemic classes. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy that is established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Richards and Schwartz (2002) emphasizes that a fundamental ethical requirement of all research should be scientifically sound. The research must be properly designed and carried out by researchers with adequate levels of expertise and supervision. It should be worth doing in a sense that the result

generates tangible benefits. In addition, Sanjari (2014) informed that consent has been recognized as an integral part of ethics in research carried out in different fields. For qualitative researchers, it is of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data will be collected and how they are to be used. He also stated that informed consent is a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent is not possible and where it is felt that the benefits of the research outweigh the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent be obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions which are likely to be asked, the use to which the results

will be put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances will be used in reports. Participants should also be given time to both consider their participation and to ask questions of the researcher. In this study, the researcher would follow the ethical considerations as part of the process in qualitative research. It was the responsibility of the researcher to completely inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in comprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results will be published and used. In same manner, this study will be submitted to the ethics committee of the Rizal Memorial College, graduate school for verification and approval.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other

occasions reliving past experiences may be difficult. However the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or obser-

vational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the home economics teachers from Cluster 3, Paquibato District, Davao City. Second is the

access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The selected HE teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the

storing of data; Davidson's (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected after the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, but still, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The face-to-face collection of data or the virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing was followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the video call via messenger, Viber, zoom, or Google Meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger

units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is

that it's a flexible method which can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources,

which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes meth-

ods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own

resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This tech-

nique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and

be proud of. Credibility is how confident the qualitative researcher is in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability is how the quali-

Figure 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

tative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students' perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address that core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher

which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability is based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability is the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) states that dependability deals with the core issue that "the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussions

This part of the research dealt with the research questions and its answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The participants unraveled their experiences as they revealed their views on strengthening the life skills of the learners in Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City.

3.1. Experiences of HE teachers in strengthening the life skills of the students in the post pandemic class—

3.1.1. Practicing good communication— The practice of good communication inside the classroom brings about a big difference in relaying important messages in and out of the classroom. The communication is practiced inside the classroom, the more the learners understand the topics being discussed during class hours. Proper classroom communication un-

leashes the learning process of every student. It enables the learners to raise questions in its simplest form and are answered immediately by the teachers. Given this kind of communication inside the classrooms unlocks the learning difficulties of the learners. It only takes courage and motivation to make the learners practice a straightforward inquiry. For participant T1,

she observed that there was a kind of feeling being awkward in communication inside her classroom. Especially when the learners came back to face-to-face classes. In the past two years, the learners were left on their own and there was no actual discussion and interface of the learners and teachers. As for T3, she just allowed the learners to exchange their simple ideas and participate in the group discussions.

3.1.2. Strengthening food preparation techniques—One of the common experiences of home economics teachers during the initial stages of face-to-face classes was to strengthen the food preparation techniques of the learners. While the learners were all out of the campus for the past two years, the learners may have learned important cooking procedures at home through the direct supervision of their parents or siblings. For them, they had to strengthen their skills and techniques in food preparation. The learners were observed to have demonstrated their cooking methods, however, there was a need to correct or improve their food processing techniques. The response of T2 suggests that she noticed the skills of the learners in doing their food preparations. They were excited to show their cooking skills during the laboratory classes. As for T4, she allowed and supervised the learners prepare their food, they felt the excitement of being back to school. T6 on the other hand presented several classroom activi-

3.1.3. Guided and appropriate decision making—Decision making skills of the learners, although they are till young were properly guided. These decision-making skills of the learners were based on their age and academic levels. They were properly guided as to what and how they prepared their food procedures. These simple decision-making skills were directly supervised by the home economics teachers. It can be noticed that the teachers where

For T5, she felt the excitement as she started her face-to-face classes. Encouraging her learners to talk and discuss the topics of the day. Radun (2019) discussed that our words have the power to build our loved ones up and guide our communications in the right direction, or they can have the opposite effect. But our words only account for 7

ties, she too supervised and checked the procedures. Chenhall (2010) reported that home food preparation skills and behavior were measured using four variables: confidence with eight cooking techniques, confidence with cooking 10 foods, ability to prepare different dishes without help, and frequency of cooking main meals. Over the past several decades, a transition or change in cooking and food preparation skills has been hypothesized and observed, which could have an important impact on healthy eating and the health of Canadians, presently and in the future. This transition in cooking and food preparation skills involves the increased use of pre-prepared, packaged and convenience foods, which require fewer and/or different skills than what is often referred to as traditional or 'from scratch' cooking. Several technological, food system-related and broader shifts within the social, economic, physical and cultural environments have been identified as factors influencing the culture of cooking and food preparation within the home or domestic environment.

always on the move as they guided their class learners decide on simple steps or processes inside their classrooms. For T1, she permitted her learners to take a simple decision making in their own ways. As for T5, she gave the decision making on what to prepare and how to prepare their class activities with minimal supervision. Finally, T7 tolerated her learners to practice their cooking skills in their own ways with her strict direct supervision. Guid-

ing them although out the food preparations. Kaplan (2023) explained that Decision-making skills are the soft skills that you can use to help solve every problem at a company. Whether an employee needs to choose what font is best for a brand logo or what growth marketing tactic to use, making good decisions is crucial to company success. Decision-making skills are all of the skills you need to make an informed, rational decision. Someone with good decision-making skills at work can assess all the facts, understand the company's current state and goal state, and choose the best course of action. Decision-making is about much more than the final result. Numerous types of skills go into decision-making, including analysis, cre-

ativity, collaboration, and leadership skills. Herity (2023) discussed that the ability to make decisions is a valuable leadership trait and it demonstrates your capacity to think objectively and weigh different options. In addition, your aptitude to make a quick decision can help establish a strong bond of trust with others that can strengthen your culture. You actually incorporate a wide variety of skills during the course of making decisions. The following skills contribute to decision-making and are good things to highlight on your resume: Problem-solving, Leadership, Reasoning, Intuition, Teamwork, Emotional Intelligence, Creativity, Time management and Organization.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the students*—The home economics teachers were very much aware that after more than two years of non-face to face classes, the learners may have some apprehensions in coming back to school. Much to

their dismay, some of the learners were hesitant to go back to school, some were also excited to return to school. These experiences of the home economics teachers led them to develop a few coping mechanisms to help them adjust with the current learners and even parents' hesitancy to go back to school.

3.2.1. *Building students' capacity*—one of the coping mechanisms developed by the home economics teachers was focused on building students' capacity. Given the experiences of the learners while they were home schooled, some of them were not confident to perform school activities although they were noted to have been performing well during the pre-COVID school year. According to T2, most of the learners felt awkward during the start of their classes, they were encouraged to join the groups and perform the activities along with their classmates. For T3, she encouraged them to perform activities with their classmates, she made them decide how to do procedures on their own. While T6 observed that the learners were capable of performing their class tasks well, she had drawn

their ideas first prior to their class task performances. Instructional change needs space and time to take root. When educators take risks on new teaching strategies, it opens space to welcome students as collaborators. Supportive teacher-to-teacher relationships are a key component for enabling students. It is important for teachers to collaboratively investigate new teaching methods and equally important for administrators to be open to what teachers offer. Empowered teachers lead to empowered students (Gallup Student Poll, 2015). BrainWare Learning Company (2023) elucidated that Cognitive skills are the foundation for learning. They are the processes our brains use to take in, store, organize, comprehend and retrieve information, as well as to make decisions and

Figure 3. Experiences of HE teachers in strengthening the life skills of the students in the post pandemic class

take action. Cognitive skills include processes like different types of attention, various aspects of visual and auditory processing, short-term and long-term memory and executive functions, including working memory, inhibitory control and cognitive flexibility, among others. Each

3.2.2. Open to feedback—The home economics teachers managed their classes through open feedbacking. The learners usually complained and asked questions during their class hours. We are all aware that some of the learners were not confident to raise questions during lectures and laboratory activities. Through open feedbacking, the learners began asking questions about the procedures and some of them even discussed their understanding about the lessons. This was one of the most effective coping mechanisms of the teachers to regain their learner's classroom confidence after being out of their classrooms for several months. For teachers 4,6 and 7, they encouraged their learners to provide their comments, suggestions or feedback about their class tasks. Some of these learners openly expressed their difficulties encountered during their food preparation processes. The learners were made to speak out their ideas. It was observed that the more the learners spoke about their experiences in per-

3.2.3. Focus on basic life skills for the 21st century—Being in the 21st century, it is important that we learn the basics of life survival. The development of Life skills plays a significant role in our lives. The more we learn these skills, the better chances we have for a good life in this ever changing environment. According to T1, she focused in developing the skills of the learners through simple procedures. She recalled that she highlighted communicating, budgeting and marketing. T2, on the other hand emphasized skills in communication technol-

cognitive skill contributes to the learning capacity of the individual, as does the degree to which they work together. Each of us has cognitive strengths and weaknesses or stronger and weaker learning skills.

forming the home economics tasks, the more they were able to practice their being open to their ideas. Clark-Jones (2015) cited that feedback doesn't just happen; you have to make it happen. Anytime you speak or act, there is an opportunity to receive constructive feedback. This can be scary for some of us but not if you remember that the person you are typically asking for the feedback from knows you and may have valuable information to share. Once you receive constructive feedback, accept it and express your appreciation for their willingness to provide this helpful information. Do not let the feedback (no matter how unpleasant) affect your opinion of the person who is offering input. The ultimate goal is to learn from feedback. Make it a habit to ask for constructive feedback, even when you think everything is going well. Be patient with yourself as you implement the suggested changes and recommendations. This can take time, but in the end your relationships will be better for the effort.

ogy, these were important for the learners to facilitate their learning. They should at least learn how to browse the internet and learn techniques in cooking through their researches and Youtube videos. For T3, teaching the learners with the 21st century skills were not totally difficult, the learners were fast to absorb the facts of their activities. Thoughtful learning (2023) postulated that Life skills equip students to thrive in the classroom and in the world beyond. The 21st century life skills are flexibility, initiative, social skills, productivity, and leadership. Flexibility,

Given the rapid rate of change in our world, the ability to adjust and adapt is critical to success. Students need to learn to quickly analyze what is going on around them and make adjustments on the fly all the while keeping their goals at the forefront of their minds. Initiative, the entrepreneurial spirit is founded on initiative the willingness to step forward with an idea and take the risk of bringing it to fruition. The changing economic landscape requires entrepreneurs. Students need to learn how to set goals for themselves, plan how they will reach their goals, and enact their plans. Once students feel comfortable with charting their own course, they will readily launch into activity. Social Skills, Human being have always been social creatures, connecting to and depending on a tribe of some hundred others. Technology now allows people to belong to multiple tribes—students at the same school, friends on Facebook, colleagues on LinkedIn, fans on fan sites, gamers on massively multiplayer online games. Buckle (2022) explained that concept of "21st century skills" isn't new skills like critical thinking, collaboration, and problem solving have been taught in classrooms for decades. 21st century skills refer to the knowledge, life skills, career skills, habits, and traits that are critically important to

student success in today's world, particularly as students move on to college, the workforce, and adult life. Generally, however, educators agree that schools must weave these skills into learning experiences and common core instruction. Here is a non-exhaustive list of the most commonly cited 21st century skills. Critical thinking Communication skills, Creativity, Problem solving, Perseverance, Collaboration, Information literacy, Technology skills and digital literacy, Media literacy, Global awareness, Self-direction, social skills, Literacy skills, Civic literacy, social responsibility, Innovation skills and Thinking skills. Corgi (2023) explained the importance of critical thinking, teamwork, creativity, and other "21st-century skills." These skills are acknowledged to be essential to thrive in today's world. However, you might be asking what those super skills are and how you can master them. The role of 21st-century education is to help every student learn how to learn. Modern learning encourages collaboration, inspires creativity, and rewards critical thinking. It teaches students how to make sense of the never-ending flow of information and use it wisely. By providing students with these fundamental abilities, 21st-century education helps them thrive in the workplace.

3.3. Insights drawn to educate the HE learners from the chronicles of the teachers— The insights gained from the narratives of the teacher participants were worth keeping for the betterment of the teaching and learning of

home economics as a course. Understanding the millennials characteristics plays an important role of their survival in this very demanding times. The enhancement of practical skills comes along with constant practice and outpouring of the ideas of the learners.

3.3.1. Understanding the millennial characteristics— Getting to know the different characteristics of the millennials are important in teaching nowadays. It is important that the teachers know the wants and needs of the learners whether inside or outside their classrooms. It

will take time to really get to know the learners' ways in learning. It takes courage patience for the teachers to understand these young learners. The insight of T1 was found to be significant in keeping the learners' attention to school activities. She considered the constant exposure

Figure 4. Coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the students

of the learner to technology particularly on the cellular phones and internet browsing. These gadgets could no longer be taken away, but it is there to stay. As for T4, she realized that each learner is special in a way that they are all different in terms of their character traits. For T5, there is a need for the teachers to learn new technologies, unlearn the old teaching practices and relearn the good old habits. Much has been said about the millennial generation: Entitled and impulsive. Ambitious yet lazy. Classic narcissists who refuse to grow up. The word millennial itself has continuously been used in the media to discredit and belittle this entire group of individuals born between 1981 to 1996. Regardless of the negative reputation millennials, in general, seem to effortlessly attract, the fact remains that they will soon dominate the workforce. With a population of 35 million strong, Filipino millennials, or Filennials, are ready to shake and reshape the country's economic landscape. According to a 2015 census by the Philippine Statistics Authority, Filennials comprise 53Fuscaldo (2023) described millennials as those born between 1981 and 1996, millennials are the largest living group at 83.1 million strong. They are tech savvy, care about more than just a paycheck, and are accustomed to having a voice and seat at the table. They're an optimistic group who love social media and

3.3.2. *Enhance practical life skills*—. Enhancing practical life skills of learners will benefit all of them in the future. Since there is a rapid changing economics, political, social and academic processes, living in this world requires a lot of practical skills to survive. These life skills are necessary if we, as elders try our very best to educate the learners on the actual realities of life in this millennium. The insight of T2 was considered a significant contribution to the new educational management. The consideration of enhancing the practical skills of

want their jobs and encounters to have meaning. Learn how millennials have influenced the workplace and their current role in today's workforce. It's important to know the best ways to manage them. Millennials make up more than one-third of the workforce and play an important role in the U.S. economy. Managing millennials in the workplace requires business owners to be transparent, flexible and willing to embrace technology. Millennials are fickle. They are willing to job hop if they aren't satisfied in their current role. "Millennials," "Generation Y," "Generation WE," "The Boomerang Generation," "The Peter Pan Generation" we go by many names and were born roughly between 1980 and 2000. Millennials are multitasking pros and can juggle many responsibilities at once. This also means that we are easily distracted and find social media and texting hard to resist. Millennials know everything there is to know about social media because we are living it. We are constantly perusing Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc. it's how we share and get information. Millennials are the most curious generation in the workforce today. And since research shows this soft skill plays a vital role in a company's success leading to fewer bad decisions, more innovation, and stronger team performance it's worth paying attention to during the hiring process (Abbot, 2022).

the learners is deemed necessary to make them survive in this demanding time and society. T3 noticed that most of the teachers have focused on the theories of their courses and forgetting the practical side of their lectures or teachings. For T6, the enhancement of practical skills is intended to prepare them for the life changing eventualities. Positive Action is a complete educational program focused on teaching life skills to students from preschool through high school. By using Positive Action's life skills curriculum in your school, you'll help each student

become aware of their own abilities, which will set them up for success in life. The Positive Action life skills curriculum works for students of all ages, young and old. As a student's first time in a classroom, it's important that preschool provides young children with the communication and social skills training they'll need throughout their education. For young students in grade levels kindergarten through fifth, skill-based kits teach them new interpersonal skills using group tasks and stories of relatable characters in various scenarios. Together, they will add new problem-solving, personal health, and goal-setting skills to their tools collection (Positive Action Inc, 2023). Ramnani (2023) postulated

that practical knowledge can often lead to a deeper understanding of a concept through the act of personal experience. Theoretical learning is what the knowledge is about and the practical application is how the knowledge learnt needs to be implemented in certain real-life situations. The mode of practical application along with theory gives everyone a clear explanation about the facts. Theory teaches about the experiences of others while by practically experiencing the particular task you can build your own experiences. Philosophically, knowledge is intangible but the practical application made it tangible by applying those skills in practice.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to explore the views of home economics teachers in enhancing the life skills of the learners in Cluster 13, Paquibato District, Davao City. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Creswell's (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of the teacher's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own ideas on the phenomenon being explored which were the ways and means of teachers in strengthening the life skills of the learners in their respective schools.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of thematic analysis of the responses of the home economics teacher participants as to their experiences, challenges and insights about their strategies in strengthening the life skills of their learners, the following themes on the HE teachers' experiences emerged: Practicing good communication, strengthening food preparation techniques and guided and appropriate decision

making. The coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the students were: building students' capacity, opening to feedback and focusing on basic life skills for the 21st century. The insights drawn from the participants were: understanding the millennial characteristics and enhance practical life skills.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of HE teachers in strengthening the life skills of the students in the post pandemic class revealed three significant themes. The first one was on practicing good commu-

nication. It is in real sense that this time, a good communication is one of the key factors in teaching and learning. The better the communication flow between the teacher and the students, even with the parents and other school stakeholders, the better would be the under-

Figure 5. Insights drawn to educate the HE learners from the chronicles of the teachers

standing of everyone involved in the school activities. An open communication leads everyone to where the objectives of the course was intended. Along this line, the communication that is well established lessens classroom or school problems since everyone who is involved in the class activities are well informed. The second theme identified in this part of the research was on strengthening food preparation skills of the learners. It is well understood that in a home economics class, the students are expected to perform course tasks based on the activities lined up for them in a particular grading period. Food preparation skills are important not only for individual survival but for the future. Nobody knows what lies beyond tomorrow. These food preparation skills may help them in building their dreams in the future as a food entrepreneur. A good cook means so much for each family to enjoy their food without spending too much. It is just a matter of cooking techniques that make the family meal sumptuous and nutritious. The third theme identified in the part of the research was about being guided and making appropriate decision making. The class does only focus on cooking skills but this course includes proper decision making. It is true that being able to decide what to cook, how to cook and when to cook are simple decisions but requires a good reasoning. With due consideration to the inflation rate we are experiencing this time, it is important to decide, in its simplest manner, the right meal to be served. Being able to decide which food and be prepared for the entire family provides the best home cooked meal with a low budget and yet, nutritious and healthy for everyone. The coping mechanisms of HE teachers in enhancing the life skills of the learners revealed three themes. The first was on building learners' capacity. For the HE teachers to cope with the dwindling attention of the learners in the course, they opted to start building the learners capacity to do things on their own. As teachers, they knew the capacities of their learners as being alone, being a part of the team or group. It is a common knowledge that everyone must possess a skill to survive in this very demanding society. Despite the learners tender age, they were gradually developed by the teachers starting from the basic skills of cooking to a bit more complex procedures. The second coping mechanism of the teachers was about being open to feedback. We are all aware that most of the learners choose to be quiet rather than be more outspoken of their classroom experiences. Human beings as we are, there are times that we stand to be corrected. There is a need for the teachers to open the communication channel to get to know more of the learners' ideas and queries about the subject matter. As soon as we hear the comments or feedbacks of the learners, we are also learning from their comments. The third coping mechanism of the HE teachers was on focusing on the basic life skills for the 21st century. Basic life skills are important for survival in this demanding times. Without these basic life skills, living in this generation would be difficult, if not dangerous for survival. Having learners develop these skills at home and reinforced in the school assures us that these learners can live with the healthy and happy life despite the economic and health downturn of our community or country. The basic procedures in cooking, marketing, food processing and preservation, proper choice of food couples with proper food handling are just a few of the basic life skills our learners need to develop. People nowadays cannot solely rely on the food sold on line or prepared by others. They need to have skills in the kitchen to make them survive. The insights drawn from the HE teachers revealed two significant factors. One is on understanding the characteristics of millennials. We teachers cannot simply jump into conclusion. There is a need to analyze every situation where we are. A clear view on the character of the learners would help us understand their ways of doing things. We teachers

cannot assume anything unless we know very well our students while they are inside the classroom. These learners are immersed in different technological activities. As teachers, we have to solicit their ideas and utilize their individual skills in browsing the internet of their gadgets. This makes our lives as teachers easier since they are all skilled in using these technologies. They have a better understanding in the utilization of these instruments. The second insights determined from this research was on enhancing the learners' practical skills. These learners are

mostly techno savvy, this means that they use their hand-held gadgets with utmost precision and skill. As teachers, we have to watch out on the learners' practical skills. Some of these learners are reliant on their parents and other people to do things for them. There is a need to train these learners to acquire to love the art of cooking and food preparation and even simple home management skills. Without these practical skills, life would be miserable for them in the future.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The findings of the study as to the experiences of home economics teachers in strengthening the life skills of the learners, the teachers coping mechanisms and insights may provide a great information to the following entities: The DepEd Personnel and School Heads may allocate more time for the teachers to be trained in their respective school division in terms of handling and delivering the elementary home economics curriculum with due consideration to the current situation of the school, teachers expertise and environment and personal background of the learner. The home economics teachers may be more proactive in implementing the course to their learners. The teachers may be more sen-

sitive to the needs of the learners and be watchful on the skills of the learners. These teachers may consider the personal characteristics of the learners and guide them to improve their home economics skills gradually. The parents may be guided by the teachers through constant meetings to unravel the learning difficulties of their children and help them reach their goals in educating their children and make them more independent. The home economics learners may be guided properly to enrich their knowledge in home economics, that this course is not only intended to improve their skills in cooking but being more knowledgeable on how to live and be healthy. For the future researchers, a similar study may be conducted in other regions or divisions. The researchers may consider other stakeholders as participants. Studies on the parents cooking skills and food preferences may be explored.

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